

MC13C3	Mario Castro	6-8	1	260	189.1	15	10.91	37.5	15	0.104	0.064	0.96	0.01	2.00	2.54
<u>MC13C4</u>	Mario Castro	8-10	1	240	174.5	15	10.91	37.5	15	3.245	3.205	48.075	0.53	92.30	117.58
MC14C1	Mario Castro	0-4	1	435	331.4	15	11.43	31.3	15	0.068	0.028	0.42	0.00	1.46	1.86
MC14C2	Mario Castro	4-6	1	240	168.0	15	10.50	42.9	15	0.237	0.197	2.955	0.03	5.67	7.23
MC14C3	Mario Castro	6-8	1	230	167.3	15	10.91	37.5	15	0.088	0.048	0.72	0.01	1.32	1.69
<u>MC14C4</u>	Mario Castro	8-10	1	330	235.7	15	10.71	40.0	15	3.447	3.407	51.105	0.57	134.92	171.87
MC15C1	Mario Castro	0-4	1	475	371.7	15	11.74	27.8	15	0.108	0.068	1.02	0.01	3.88	4.94
MC15C2	Mario Castro	4-6	1	180	135.0	15	11.25	33.3	15	0.215	0.175	2.625	0.03	3.78	4.82
MC15C3	Mario Castro	6-8	1	245	186.7	15	11.43	31.3	15	0.111	0.071	1.065	0.01	2.09	2.66
<u>MC15C4</u>	Mario Castro	8-10	1	215	161.3	15	11.25	33.3	15	3.684	3.644	54.66	0.58	94.02	119.76
MC16C1	Mario Castro	0-4	1	435	310.7	15	10.71	40.0	15	0.186	0.146	2.19	0.02	7.62	9.71
MC16C2	Mario Castro	4-6	1	345	246.4	15	10.71	40.0	15	0.297	0.257	3.855	0.04	10.64	13.55
MC16C3	Mario Castro	6-8	1	155	110.7	15	10.71	40.0	15	0.083	0.043	0.645	0.01	0.80	1.02
<u>MC16C4</u>	Mario Castro	8-10	1	355	253.6	15	10.71	40.0	15	1.816	1.776	26.64	0.30	75.66	96.38
MC17C1	Mario Castro	0-4	1	465	327.2	15	10.56	42.1	15	0.045	0.005	0.075	0.00	0.28	0.36
MC17C2	Mario Castro	4-6	1	265	192.7	15	10.91	37.5	15	0.183	0.143	2.145	0.02	4.55	5.79
MC17C3	Mario Castro	6-8	1	215	156.4	15	10.91	37.5	15	1.087	1.047	15.705	0.17	27.01	34.41
<u>MC17C4</u>	Mario Castro	8-10	1	260	182.0	15	10.50	42.9	15	2.769	2.729	40.935	0.47	85.14	108.46
MC18C1	Mario Castro	0-4	1	465	420.7	15	13.57	10.5	15	1.674	1.634	24.51	0.22	91.18	116.15
MC18C2	Mario Castro	4-6	1	260	189.1	15	10.91	37.5	15	0.091	0.051	0.765	0.01	1.59	2.03
MC18C3	Mario Castro	6-8	1	255	194.3	15	11.43	31.3	15	0.15	0.11	1.65	0.02	3.37	4.29
<u>MC18C4</u>	Mario Castro	8-10	1	325	227.5	15	10.50	42.9	15	1.837	1.797	26.955	0.31	70.08	89.28
MC19C1	Mario Castro	0-4	1	465	348.8	15	11.25	33.3	15	2.099	2.059	30.885	0.33	114.89	146.36
MC19C2	Mario Castro	4-6	1	255	191.3	15	11.25	33.3	15	0.088	0.048	0.72	0.01	1.47	1.87
MC19C3	Mario Castro	6-8	1	250	190.5	15	11.43	31.3	15	0.165	0.125	1.875	0.02	3.75	4.78
<u>MC19C4</u>	Mario Castro	8-10	1	330	255.0	15	11.59	29.4	15	2.902	2.862	42.93	0.44	113.34	144.38
H1C1	Halcón	0-4	1	560	402.5	15	10.78	39.1	15	0.223	0.183	2.745	0.03	12.30	15.67
H1C2	Halcón	4-6	1	260	191.6	15	11.05	35.7	15	1.178	1.138	17.07	0.19	35.51	45.23
H1C3	Halcón	6-8	1	195	145.0	15	11.15	34.5	15	0.291	0.251	3.765	0.04	5.87	7.48
<u>H1C4</u>	Halcón	8-10	1	205	150.3	15	11.00	36.4	15	0.418	0.378	5.67	0.06	9.30	11.85
H2C1	Halcón	0-4	1	525	377.3	15	10.78	39.1	15	0.096	0.056	0.84	0.01	3.53	4.49
H2C2	Halcón	4-6	1	250	175.9	15	10.56	42.1	15	0.805	0.765	11.475	0.13	22.95	29.24
H2C3	Halcón	6-8	1	205	146.4	15	10.71	40.0	15	1.274	1.234	18.51	0.21	30.36	38.67
<u>H2C4</u>	Halcón	8-10	1	195	140.4	15	10.80	38.9	15	0.247	0.207	3.105	0.03	4.84	6.17
H3C1	Halcón	0-4	1	575	416.4	15	10.86	38.1	15	0.126	0.086	1.29	0.01	5.93	7.56
H3C2	Halcón	4-6	1	275	122.2	15	6.67	125.0	15	0.051	0.011	0.165	0.00	0.36	0.46
H3C3	Halcón	6-8	1	170	121.4	15	10.71	40.0	15	1.011	0.971	14.565	0.16	19.81	25.23
<u>H3C4</u>	Halcón	8-10	1	195	141.8	15	10.91	37.5	15	0.68	0.64	9.6	0.11	14.98	19.08
H4C1	Halcón	0-4	1	510	374.0	15	11.00	36.4	15	0.106	0.066	0.99	0.01	4.04	5.15
H4C2	Halcón	4-6	1	235	176.3	15	11.25	33.3	15	0.028	-0.012	-0.18	0.00	-0.34	0.00
H4C3	Halcón	6-8	1	245	176.4	15	10.80	38.9	15	0.336	0.296	4.44	0.05	8.70	11.09
<u>H4C4</u>	Halcón	8-10	1	305	213.5	15	10.50	42.9	15	0.507	0.467	7.005	0.08	17.09	21.77
H5C1	Halcón	0-4	1	410	287.0	15	10.50	42.9	15	0.099	0.059	0.885	0.01	2.90	3.70
H5C2	Halcón	4-6	1	235	167.9	15	10.71	40.0	15	0	-0.04	-0.6	-0.01	-1.13	0.00
H5C3	Halcón	6-8	1	225	168.8	15	11.25	33.3	15	0.618	0.578	8.67	0.09	15.61	19.88
<u>H5C4</u>	Halcón	8-10	1	325	243.8	15	11.25	33.3	15	0.726	0.686	10.29	0.11	26.75	34.08
H6C1	Halcón	0-4	1	385	275.0	15	10.71	40.0	15	0.227	0.187	2.805	0.03	8.64	11.01
H6C2	Halcón	4-6	1	205	164.0	15	12.00	25.0	15	0.061	0.021	0.315	0.00	0.52	0.66
H6C3	Halcón	6-8	1	215	163.8	15	11.43	31.3	15	1.042	1.002	15.03	0.16	25.85	32.93
<u>H6C4</u>	Halcón	8-10	1	220	167.6	15	11.43	31.3	15	0.572	0.532	7.98	0.08	14.04	17.89
H7C1	Halcón	0-4	1	455	341.3	15	11.25	33.3	15	0.326	0.286	4.29	0.05	15.62	19.89
H7C2	Halcón	4-6	1	195	141.8	15	10.91	37.5	15	0.077	0.037	0.555	0.01	0.87	1.10
H7C3	Halcón	6-8	1	265	201.9	15	11.43	31.3	15	0.17	0.13	1.95	0.02	4.13	5.27

H7C4	Halcón	8-10	1	310	218.1	15	10.56	42.1	15	0.088	0.048	0.72	0.01	1.79	2.27
H8C1	Halcón	0-4	1	430	322.5	15	11.25	33.3	15	1.465	1.425	21.375	0.23	73.53	93.67
H8C2	Halcón	4-6	1	210	157.5	15	11.25	33.3	15	0.046	0.006	0.09	0.00	0.15	0.19
H8C3	Halcón	6-8	1	275	196.4	15	10.71	40.0	15	0	-0.04	-0.6	-0.01	-1.32	0.00
H8C4	Halcón	8-10	1	325	227.5	15	10.50	42.9	15	0.245	0.205	3.075	0.04	8.00	10.18
H9C1	Halcón	0-4	1	365	273.8	15	11.25	33.3	15	0.309	0.269	4.035	0.04	11.78	15.01
H9C2	Halcón	4-6	1	250	187.5	15	11.25	33.3	15	0.003	-0.037	-0.555	-0.01	-1.11	0.00
H9C3	Halcón	6-8	1	255	191.3	15	11.25	33.3	15	0	-0.04	-0.6	-0.01	-1.22	0.00
H9C4	Halcón	8-10	1	295	214.5	15	10.91	37.5	15	0.257	0.217	3.255	0.04	7.68	9.79
H10C1	Halcón	0-4	1	440	345.7	15	11.79	27.3	15	0.866	0.826	12.39	0.13	43.61	55.56
H10C2	Halcón	4-6	1	205	156.2	15	11.43	31.3	15	0.035	-0.005	-0.075	0.00	-0.12	0.00
H10C3	Halcón	6-8	1	230	176.9	15	11.54	30.0	15	0.014	-0.026	-0.39	0.00	-0.72	0.00
H10C4	Halcón	8-10	1	310	232.5	15	11.25	33.3	15	0.306	0.266	3.99	0.04	9.90	12.61
H11C1	Halcón	0-4	1	460	334.5	15	10.91	37.5	15	0.899	0.859	12.885	0.14	47.42	60.40
H11C2	Halcón	4-6	1	245	169.6	15	10.38	44.4	15	0.083	0.043	0.645	0.01	1.26	1.61
H11C3	Halcón	6-8	1	230	164.3	15	10.71	40.0	15	0	-0.04	-0.6	-0.01	-1.10	0.00
H11C4	Halcón	8-10	1	300	208.7	15	10.43	43.8	15	0.075	0.035	0.525	0.01	1.26	1.61
H12C1	Halcón	0-4	1	530	402.8	15	11.40	31.6	15	0.107	0.067	1.005	0.01	4.26	5.43
H12C2	Halcón	4-6	1	220	162.6	15	11.09	35.3	15	0	-0.04	-0.6	-0.01	-1.06	0.00
H12C3	Halcón	6-8	1	220	167.6	15	11.43	31.3	15	0.009	-0.031	-0.465	0.00	-0.82	0.00
H12C4	Halcón	8-10	1	325	240.2	15	11.09	35.3	15	0.442	0.402	6.03	0.07	15.68	19.97
H13C1	Halcón	0-4	1	525	388.0	15	11.09	35.3	15	0.108	0.068	1.02	0.01	4.28	5.46
H13C2	Halcón	4-6	1	215	153.6	15	10.71	40.0	15	0.01	-0.03	-0.45	-0.01	-0.77	0.00
H13C3	Halcón	6-8	1	225	160.7	15	10.71	40.0	15	0	-0.04	-0.6	-0.01	-1.08	0.00
H13C4	Halcón	8-10	1	300	214.3	15	10.71	40.0	15	0.473	0.433	6.495	0.07	15.59	19.86
H14C1	Halcón	0-4	1	395	319.8	15	12.14	23.5	15	0.374	0.334	5.01	0.05	15.83	20.17
H14C2	Halcón	4-6	1	215	166.1	15	11.59	29.4	15	0.003	-0.037	-0.555	-0.01	-0.95	0.00
H14C3	Halcón	6-8	1	220	174.2	15	11.88	26.3	15	0	-0.04	-0.6	-0.01	-1.06	0.00
H14C4	Halcón	8-10	1	230	174.8	15	11.40	31.6	15	0.64	0.6	9	0.09	16.56	21.10
H15C1	Halcón	0-4	1	425	354.2	15	12.50	20.0	15	0.424	0.384	5.76	0.06	19.58	24.95
H15C2	Halcón	4-6	1	235	203.0	15	12.95	15.8	15	0.016	-0.024	-0.36	0.00	-0.68	0.00
H15C3	Halcón	6-8	1	210	171.8	15	12.27	22.2	15	0	-0.04	-0.6	-0.01	-1.01	0.00
H15C4	Halcón	8-10	1	190	164.1	15	12.95	15.8	15	0.147	0.107	1.605	0.01	2.44	3.11

Blank: N-NO₃
0.040 mg/L